

Laboratory Determination of Rock Fracture Shear Stiffness using Seismic Wave Propagation and Digital Image Correlation

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Abstract

Seismic wave propagation and digital image correlation were used during direct shear experiments on Indiana Limestone specimens to investigate the stiffness of rock discontinuities (fractures) approaching shear failure. An instrumented direct shear apparatus was used to apply shear stress to the discontinuity. Compressional and shear wave pulses were transmitted through and reflected from the discontinuity while digital images of the specimen surface were acquired during the test. To measure the dynamic shear stiffness of the rock discontinuities, the displacement discontinuity theory was used and the stiffness was calculated based on the ratio of transmitted to reflected wave amplitudes. The static shear stiffness was calculated based on the ratio of an increment in the applied shear stress to the corresponding increment of relative shear displacement (slip) along the discontinuity. The dynamic shear stiffness measured by seismic wave propagation showed roughly five to ten times greater magnitude than the static values measured by digital image correlation technique. This observation is found to be in agreement with available studies indicating that the frequency-dependent fracture stiffness arises from probabilistic and spatial distributions of stiffness and that dynamic moduli are typically greater than the static values.

Keywords: *Seismic wave propagation, Digital image correlation, Static shear stiffness, Dynamic shear stiffness, Rock fracture, Rock discontinuity*

1. Introduction

The mechanical, hydraulic, and geophysical properties of rock discontinuities (fractures) are controlled by fracture surface roughness, contact area among fracture surfaces, and the aperture distribution of the void space in the fracture (Kendall and Tabor 1971; Schoenberg 1980; Raven and Gale 1895; Barton et al. 1985; Brown 1987; Pyrak-Nolte et al., 1987; Hopkins, 1990; Pyrak-Nolte et al. 1990; Cook, 1992; Zimmerman et al. 1992; Renshaw, 1995; Pyrak-Nolte and Morris 2000; Nakagawa et al. 2000; Liu 2005; Yoshioka and Iwasa 2006; Nagata et al. 2008; Luo et al. 2016; Pyrak-Nolte and Nolte 2016). The terms fracture, discontinuity and joint are used interchangeably in rock mechanics and consequently in this paper. Fracture stiffness is a term that is used to describe the geometry of the fracture, as introduced by Goodman et al. (1968). The stiffness of a fracture is defined as the ratio of the increment of stress to the increment of displacement caused by the deformation of the void space in the fracture (Pyrak-Nolte & Morris, 2000). Fracture Stiffness is an effective parameter that depends on contact area and aperture distribution and stiffness provides a link to the hydraulic response of a fracture (Pyrak-Nolte and Morris 2000; Petrovitch et al. 2013; Petrovitch et al. 2014; Pyrak-Nolte and Nolte 2016). The fracture stiffness definitions mentioned above are valid for both static and dynamic loading conditions when the stress distribution is nearly uniform with very small spatial variations in stress and the fracture response does not depend on frequency (Nakagawa 1998). Frequency dependence is affected by scattering of the wavefront from the geometry of the fracture which does not occur in static measurements.

Extensive studies have been done to investigate normal fracture stiffness, both statically and dynamically. Static approaches require subjecting the rock specimen containing a discontinuity to a normal stress and simultaneously measuring the displacements across the fracture (Hopkins et

al. 1987; Jaeger et al. 2007; Lubbe et al. 2008; Far, 2014). Dynamic approaches are based on measurements of seismic/ultrasonic waves propagated through the fractures (Pyrak-Nolte et al. 1990; Cook 1992; Nakagawa et al. 2000; Lubbe et al. 2008; Hobday and Worthington 2012; Choi et al. 2014).

Understanding the mechanical properties of rocks such as Young's moduli, normal and shear fracture stiffness, and the ratio of shear-to-normal stiffness is important for geophysical modeling, reservoir modeling, hydraulic fracturing, wellbore stability assessment, and subsidence prediction (Economides and Nolte 1989; Yale et al., 1995; Barton 2007; Choi et al. 2014). Because the magnitude of stress, deformation, and strain levels in the field are closer to the static tests than dynamic ones, the static properties are often assumed more appropriate than the dynamic ones. Thus, it is beneficial to find a correlation between the easy-to-measure dynamic stiffness and hard-to-measure static value.

Like the dynamic moduli of rock which are consistently greater than the static moduli (Economides and Nolte 1989; Ciccotti and Mulargia 2004), the dynamic normal stiffness of fractures has been found to be larger than the static normal stiffness (Pyrak-Nolte et al. 1990; Barton 2007). Studies conducted on single natural fractures in quartz-monzonite found dynamic stiffnesses four to eight times larger than the static ones (Pyrak-Nolte et al. 1990). Pyrak-Nolte and Nolte (1992) suggested that such discrepancy is, in part, due to the frequency-dependent nature of dynamic fracture stiffness. Because of the variation in the contact area over the fracture and aperture distribution of voids, different areas of fractures will have different stiffness. Different frequencies sample different subsets of the fracture and therefore the dynamic stiffness of a fracture is a frequency-dependent property (Pyrak-Nolte and Nolte 1992; Yale et al. 1995; Acosta-Colon et al. 2009).

Measurement of shear fracture specific stiffness are more complicated than the normal fracture specific stiffness. The fracture shear stiffness is scale dependent (Barton, 2007) and selecting a measurement length scale for the rock matrix and the fracture is not trivial (Choi et al. 2014). Also, lab-scale stiffness data on single natural or synthetic fractures are limited (Choi et al., 2014). Pyrak-Nolte et al. (1990) examined hydraulic, mechanical and seismic responses of fractures in quartz monzonite (Stripa granite) samples measuring 52 mm in diameter by 77 mm in height. Each specimen had a fracture oriented orthogonal to the long axis of the core. The reported values of dynamic shear fracture stiffness for dry fractures ranged from 0.95 TPa/m to 60 TPa/m (Pyrak-Nolte et al. 1990). In an effort to study the effect of combined normal and shear loading, Pyrak-Nolte (1996) observed values of about 7 to 15 TPa/m for dry fractures subjected to normal stress only and about 4-22 TPa/m for fractures subjected to both normal and shear stresses. Pyrak-Nolte (1996) hypothesized that the application of shear stress results in an increase in the shear contact in the fracture. Lubbe et al. (2008) tested synthetic fractures in Carboniferous limestone by placing two blocks of limestone in contact. The experiments were performed over a range of confining pressures (from 5 MPa up to 60 MPa), at ultrasonic frequencies in a Triaxial Hoek cell, using the pulse-echo reflection technique. They measured the dynamic fracture compliance (inverse of stiffness) and reported values of 22.036 TPa/m (compliance of 4.538×10^{-14} m/Pa) at 5 MPa of normal stress and 75.93 TPa/m (compliance of 1.317×10^{-14} m/Pa) at 60 MPa of normal stress. Choi et al. (2014) conducted a series of experiments on fractures in gypsum specimen with mated contact surfaces and examined the effect of surface roughness and loading conditions on the ratio of shear-to-normal fracture specific stiffness. Gypsum specimens were made by placing sandpaper with known grit sizes at the bottom of a mold and casting gypsum on top of the sandpaper to control the size of asperities at the contact surfaces. They reported shear fracture specific stiffness

values of 0.5 to 4 TPa/m for gypsum specimens made by sandpaper #60. Similar to the work of Pyrak-Nolte (1996), the shear stiffness was stress dependent and increased with increasing the normal stress. Similar to the lab-scale work, the field scale measurement of fracture dynamic shear stiffness have been very limited. Worthington and Hudson (2000) performed surface reflection seismic scale measurements and reported a value of 0.001 TPa/m for a major fracture zone in the Southern North Sea (Worthington and Hudson 2000). This small value is linked to the fact that the shear stiffness decreases as the fracture size increases (Worthington 2007).

In order to experimentally measure the static fracture shear stiffness, two types of tests are commonly done: (a) direct shear tests; and (b) jointed triaxial shear tests (Rosso 1974). In both types of tests, static shear stiffness is defined as the ratio of the shear stress (τ) acting of a rock joint (fracture) to the respective shear deformation (v). Since joints deform non-linearly, it is more realistic to express this relation in the following differential form: $d\tau = k_s dv$ (Kulatilake et al. 2016). It is interesting to note that static shear stiffnesses are very dependent on rock block size and are within the range of 10^{-6} to 10^{-1} TPa/m for rock joints with block sizes from 0.01-100 m (Barton 1982; Barton 2007; Melin 2012). The readers are referred to Barton (2007) for a comprehensive review of static shear stiffness. Li et al (2012) conducted jointed triaxial shear tests on drill cores of fractured tuff from Newberry Volcano and reported values of static shear stiffness as high as 0.545 TPa/m. In this study, a series of experiments was conducted on fractured specimens of Indiana limestone to investigate the feasibility of measuring the static and dynamic fracture shear stiffness of rock joints when subjected to shear failure. The primary purpose of this investigation was to provide a comparison between the experimentally measured static and dynamic shear stiffness of rock fractures using two experimental techniques: Digital image

correlation (DIC) technique for determination of the static stiffness and the seismic wave propagation method for determination of the dynamic shear stiffness.

In this paper, we present (a) the principles of DIC and its implementation, (b) the experimental procedure including the specimen properties and preparation as well as the direct shear apparatus, and (c) the experimental results and the comparison of the static and dynamic fracture shear stiffness.

2. Digital Image Correlation: Principles and Implementation

DIC is an innovative non-contact displacement measurement technique which provides the surface displacements and strains by comparing the digital images of a specimen surface taken during the experiment before and after loading/deformation (Chu et al. 1985; Pan et al. 2009; Sutton et al. 2009; Hedayat et al. 2014a). DIC is simple to use, cost effective, and commonly used to investigate deformation of engineering materials and structures. Other optical methods including both interferometric and non-interferometric techniques can also be used for surface displacement measurements (Pan et al. 2009). However, DIC has several advantages including simple experimental setup and specimen preparation, ability to work in ambient light with no special illumination, and great measurement accuracy. The theory and concepts of DIC and the process of implementing DIC including specimen preparation, image acquisition, and image processing are described below.

In DIC setup, the camera needs to be mounted perpendicular to the object surface with its optical axis on the geometric center of the specimen. The specimen surface must be planar and, most importantly, must remain in the same plane perpendicular to the camera axis during the experiment. The specimen surface must have a random pattern (texture) to provide a gray value

intensity distribution on the recorded images. The pattern can be either from the natural texture of the specimen surface or from an artificially made pattern such as a painted surface. The pattern deforms together with the specimen surface and serves to record the specimen's deformation.

After recording the digital images of the specimen surface during the experiments, DIC compares the acquired images and computes the motion of small regions of each image using a correlation algorithm (Chu et al. 1985; Tong 2005; Pan et al. 2009). The image taken before deformation at the beginning of the test is called the reference image and is used as the basis for comparison with images taken during deformation or loading.

In 2D-DIC, only one charge-coupled device (CCD) camera is needed to acquire the digital images during the experiment. Depending on the shade of grey reflected from a point on the specimen surface, a cell in the array of pixels embedded in the CCD camera stores the grey-scale value light intensity of the point. An 8-bit image has 2^8 grey-level values ranging from zero to 255. A grey-level value of 0 represents "black" and a grey-level value of 255 represents "white". A calculation area or a region of interest (ROI) needs to be defined first within the image, and the ROI is then divided into smaller portions (subsets) by an evenly spaced virtual grid so that the displacement field can be calculated at the grid points. In DIC, subsets of images are tracked between the deformed and the reference image. The reason for choosing a subset rather than a single point is that a square subset provides a unique arrangement of grey-level values that makes it identifiable compared to a single point with a single gray-level value.

To track the subset, a correlation algorithm/criterion is used. There are two types of correlation criteria that have been extensively used: (a) cross-correlation criterion (CC); and (b) sum of square

differences criterion (SSD) (Pan et al. 2009). It is worth noting that both criteria are related and both offer robust performance in calculating the displacement field.

Figure 1(a) demonstrates the process of image correlation, in which a square reference subset from the reference image is compared with the deformed subset in the deformed image. The square subset provides a wide variation of grey-level intensity values that makes it to be uniquely identifiable in the deformed image. The SSD criteria can be generally written as (Sutton 2013):

$$\Phi = \sum_{subset} [I'(x + u(x, y), y + v(x, y)) - I(x, y)]^2 \quad (1)$$

where Φ is the correlation coefficient, metric used to determine how well the subsets match, I' and I are grey-level intensity values in the deformed and undeformed subsets, and u and v are the image displacement components in pixels in x and y directions, respectively, within the subset area. When the correlation coefficient between the reference and the deformed subsets, reaches an extremum depending upon the criterion used (i.e., minimum for the SSD or maximum for the CC criterion), optimal matching is found between the two subsets. The coordinates of the extremum position define the new (displaced) position of the deformed subset. The difference between the new position of the deformed subset and the center of the reference subset yields the displacement. The same procedure is repeated for the other grid points in the ROI to obtain the full-field displacement. This procedure is demonstrated through Figure 1(b) which contains the distribution of correlation coefficients obtained from a CC criterion for a deformed subset that is translated with respect to the reference one. The peak position of the distribution of the correlation coefficient yields the new position of the deformed subset. The figure shows the peak position in the correlation distribution occurring at $u=5.2$ and $v=10.3$ pixels; where u and v are values of the x and y coordinates, respectively. This means that the deformed subset has been translated 5.2

pixels in the horizontal direction and 10.3 pixels in the vertical direction with respect to the reference subset. During the experiment, the DIC technique was used to measure deformations on the surface of a rock specimen undergoing shear failure. The DIC imaging system consisted of the following components: (1) a Grasshopper (Point Grey) CCD camera with 2448×2048 effective square pixels; (2) a 75 mm focal length lens (Model HF75SA1 Fujinon) with manual control of aperture, focus, and zoom; (3) the FlyCapture® SDK software for image acquisition; and (4) the Vic-2D software, product of Correlated Solutions, for image correlation and displacement calculation. The spatial resolution of the imaging system (i.e., the length-pixel ratio) was 80 $\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$ and the accuracy of displacement measurement system was about 1.8 μm (Hedayat et al. 2014a).

3. Experimental Procedure

3.1. Materials

In this study, the direct shear experiments were conducted on Indiana limestone specimens. Indiana limestone is a calcite-cemented calcareous rock consisting of 95-98 percent calcite (i.e., calcium carbonate, CaCO_3) and contains shell fragments that are non-crystalline. Indiana limestone is found in large quantities in Lawrence, Monroe, and Owen counties in Indiana. Although Indiana limestone is a sedimentary rock, the deposition of the minute calcareous seashell is so uniform that no weak cleavage planes occur in the material. It also has a grain direction which runs horizontally in the deposit. The Indiana limestone rock specimens for this study were taken from a mine in Bedford, Indiana operated by the Elliott Stone Company. The samples were all taken from the same quarry zone.

Being a natural rock, Indiana limestone's physical properties such as strength and porosity vary depending on texture, cementing material, and degree of moisture. Some variations in the measured unconfined compressive strength were observed in the literature for Indiana limestone specimens (Ruffolo and Shakoor 2009), as summarized in Table 1.

3.2. Specimen Preparation and Properties

Indiana limestone blocks were fractured by inducing a tensile fracture in the specimen using the setup shown in Figure 2a. This technique is similar to Brazilian testing or the split cylinder method, where two thin rods are attached to opposite sides of the specimen and a compressional load is applied along the two rods. Prior to loading, a hole was drilled through the specimen parallel to the fracture plane with a drill bit of size 6.35 mm (0.25 inch) (see Figure 2a). A tensile fracture was generated along a line between the two rods passing through the drilled hole in the middle of the specimen. The drilled hole reduced the fracturing length to half and attracted the fracture to the middle of the specimen, resulting in a nearly vertical fracture plane (see Figure 2b and 2c). Fractured specimens were created by inducing a single fracture. The fracture plane in all the specimens was created approximately parallel to the grain direction of the specimen.

After the fractures were induced, the blocks were cut to obtain specimens with dimensions 152.4 mm (6 inch) length, 127 mm (5 inch) wide, and approximately 50.8 mm (2 inch) thick. This operation was done at Cassini-D&D Mfg., Inc. in Lafayette, Indiana. The dimensions of each sample were measured using calipers with a precision up to 0.001 inches or ~25 microns. Figure 2b shows a sample of the fractured Indiana limestone specimens at the end of the preparation process. The specimens were oven-dried at temperature 90 °C for 24 hrs to remove any residual

moisture. Intact specimens with the same dimensions were also made for measuring basic geophysical properties.

Surface roughness measurements were made prior to direct shear testing using a laser profilometer available at the Purdue's Rock Physics laboratory. This profilometer had the maximum height ranges of ± 9.969 mm with the precision of $0.5 \mu\text{m}$. The measurement increment was 0.25 mm in two orthogonal directions over the entire surface. Figure 3a shows the surface roughness of the LS4 specimen (see Figure 2b) including the drilled hole in the middle of the specimen. Only one side of the fractured specimen is presented here because of the similarity between the two sides of the contact surfaces. The maximum variation from the mean (average) plane for the contact surface is ± 3 mm. The distribution of asperity heights is also shown in Figure 3b, which is a histogram of the frequency distribution of the asperity height. Asperity heights have an approximately normal distribution for the contact surface. The asperity distribution is measured for the entire contact area of the specimen excluding the drilled hole. The size of the distribution can be evaluated using the standard deviation of asperity height, which is 0.835 mm for this specimen.

3.3. Experimental setup

A direct shear apparatus was used to conduct the shear experiments on the fractured Indiana limestone specimens (Figure 4). The apparatus is a biaxial loading frame consisting of a horizontal loading frame and a universal loading machine. The horizontal loading frame was used to apply normal stress to the specimen and the contacting surfaces and the axial loading machine was used to apply the shear stress.

The horizontal frame utilized a flatjack that was connected to a hydraulic system. The flatjack was supported by steel rods and outer stiff plates, providing a reaction support for the applied load. The

applied pressure was monitored by a pressure transducers and was kept constant throughout the experiment. Another feature of this apparatus is the use of a series of rollers placed between the steel plate and the specimen assembly. The rollers were used to minimize friction between the steel plate and the assembly and to ensure that the applied shear load was transferred directly to the specimen contact surfaces. A displacement transducer was used to measure the shear displacement applied to the specimen (see Fig. 4).

During the shear experiments, the discontinuity between the two blocks in contact was constantly monitored using compressional and shear waves transmitted through and reflected off the discontinuity. The signals were continuously recorded throughout an experiment. Ten pairs of sources and receivers were housed inside loading platens on each side of the discontinuity, as shown in Figure 4. The inset in Figure 4 shows the transducer layout that was used for seismic measurements. Each source and receiver platen contained six shear wave transducers that were polarized in the direction of shear (2S, 3S, 5S, 6S, 8S, and 9S) as well as four compressional wave transducers (1P, 4P, 7P, and 10P). The main focus of this study is on determination of shear stiffness and therefore only shear transducer data is used in this study. The shear transducers had a frequency of 1 MHz (Panametrics V153RM).

Two pulser-receivers (Panametrics 5077PR), one in transmission mode and one in reflection mode, were used to excite the source with a 0.25 microsecond duration square wave with a repetition rate of 5 kHz, amplitude of 100 V and a gain of +10 dB. A data acquisition system recorded transmitted and reflected shear waves prior to and during failure of the specimen. The total time required for waveform acquisition through all 10 transducers was 0.5 seconds (i.e. sampling rate of 2 Hz).

The transducers were coupled to the surface of the specimens using oven-baked honey (Busy Bee Honey) as the coupling medium. The specimen assembly process was standardized to ensure repeatability of seismic measurements. First, the honey was dehydrated at 90°C for 90 minutes to reduce its water content and increase viscosity. A thin adhesive plastic film was placed on the surface of the testing specimen to prevent penetration of the honey into the pores of the specimen. A series of repeatability tests was performed with and without the thin plastic film to ensure that the plastic film had no significant effect on the recorded waveforms.

The normal load was applied first and was held constant throughout the test. Then, a shear displacement was imposed with a constant rate of 8 $\mu\text{m}/\text{sec}$ until failure occurred along the contact surfaces.

4. Experimental Results

4.1. Shear strength of Indiana limestone specimens

Direct shear experiments were performed on the fractured specimens under different confining stresses to determine the frictional characteristics of the contact surfaces. Figure 5a contains graphs of shear stress versus shear displacement obtained from a number of tests performed on fractured Indiana limestone specimens under normal stresses ranging from 2-4 MPa. The shear displacements were measured using the displacement transducer shown in Figure 4 and were referenced with respect to the displacement required to reach the peak shear stress. Thus, negative values of shear displacement refer to the pre-peak (pre-failure) stage of the test while positive values refer to the post-peak stage of the test.

The initial portion of the graphs in Figure 5a, i.e. -1 mm to -0.5 mm of shear displacement, shows the initial seating deformation of the specimen in the loading frame. A linear increase in shear stress with displacement occurred once the load was fully transferred to the specimen. A linear relation was observed up to the peak shear stress, or shear strength, of the discontinuity. The shear strength was reduced to its residual value in a softening regime through stick-slip oscillations. These experimental results showed that the peak value of shear stress increased as the applied normal stress increased. Based on the Coulomb friction law, the shear strength of a rock fracture can be defined by a single friction angle and a cohesion parameter. The peak and the residual failure envelopes were obtained from the regression analysis through experimental data. The results correspond to peak friction angles of 61° and residual friction angle of 55° . Because of the lack of any bonding between the contact surfaces, the regression analysis is forced to pass through the origin to account for zero cohesion (see Figure 5b).

4.2. Seismic response of specimens

Full waveform measurements were made during direct shear experiments. The transmitted and reflected waves for shear waves were recorded during the shear experiments and were analyzed to investigate the failure process along fractured Indiana limestone specimens. The direct shear experiments were performed in two stages: (a) normal loading stage in which the normal stress was gradually increased until the desired normal stress was reached; and (b) shear loading stage in which the shear stress was increased through a constant rate of shear displacement until shear failure occurred along the discontinuity.

Figure 6 shows the transmitted and reflected shear waveforms during the normal loading stage. The amplitude of the transmitted waves (Figure 6a) showed significant changes with the increase

in normal stress while less significant changes in travel time and frequency contents were observed. An increase in the transmitted wave velocity (i.e. 0.8% for 3S based on the first arrival signal) was observed because of the increase in the contact area while the change in wave velocity for the intact specimen due to the normal stress was about 0.7% for 3S. The Fourier spectra of waveforms for the fractured specimens were also studied to determine the dominant frequencies of waveforms and their variability with the applied normal stress. The dominant frequency of the signals showed a 9% increase for 3S. The increase in the applied normal stress also made small changes in the reflected waveforms (Figure 6b).

Figure 7 shows the transmitted and reflected shear waveforms recorded during shearing of the Indiana limestone specimen under 3 MPa of normal confinement.

These figures are graphs of the amplitude measured by each transducer for a given displacement (in the legend: negative values denote pre-peak and positive values post-peak displacements). The amplitude of the transmitted waves exhibited significant changes with the application of shear stress and failure. The signal arrival time and frequency content was also affected by the application of shear load. A clear reduction in the dominant frequency of the signal with shear displacement can be observed. Similar to the observations made with the reflected waves during the normal loading stage (Figure 6b), the reflected waveforms exhibited smaller changes during the shearing than the transmitted waves. The reflected shear waves recorded with transducer 3S (Figure 7b) showed a 14% variation in amplitude.

5. Seismic Wave Monitoring of Failure along the Fracture

Figure 8 shows a graph of the shear stress-displacement and the normalized peak-to-peak amplitude for an Indiana limestone specimen at a 4 MPa normal stress. The amplitude of the

transmitted wave from each transducer is normalized with respect to its maximum value during shearing. That is, a value of one indicates the maximum transmitted amplitude observed prior to the shear failure. For all the shear wave transducer pairs, the amplitude of the signals increased as the shear load was applied, i.e. after initial seating deformations (Figure 8). However, the amount of increase varied among the transducers.

A distinct peak in the normalized shear wave amplitude was observed for all shear wave transducers. These peaks are identified as premonitory seismic precursors to the impending shear failure of the discontinuity (Hedayat et al. 2014b). The precursors are linked to changes in the local normal and shear stiffness of the rock joint. Precursors can be evaluated as a function of the displacement required between their appearance and the peak shear strength. For interpretation of precursors, negative values denote the magnitude of shear displacement that is still left to reach the peak shear stress. Therefore, the more negative the value, the earlier the precursor. Close attention to the sequence of precursors also shows that the precursors occur at different times and at different shear displacements. Precursors to peak strength are observed between -0.2 mm to -0.02 mm with respect to the macroscopic failure of the discontinuity (i.e., 0 mm). Although the magnitude of the displacement may seem to be small in terms of its absolute value, it is an important fraction of the peak displacement. The average value of peak displacement for the discontinuity in the Indiana Limestone was 0.5 mm. Thus, precursors appear within the range of 60% to 96% of the peak displacement. This finding, although at the laboratory scale, is a significant contribution to the field of rock physics. The geophysical monitoring technique that was utilized provides exceptional characterization potential for understanding the shearing phenomena.

6. Fracture Specific Stiffness

6.1. Dynamic fracture stiffness measurement from seismic wave propagation

To evaluate the seismic response of rock fractures based on seismic wave measurements, the displacement discontinuity theory (Kendall and Tabor 1971; Hudson 1981; Myer et al. 1985; Pyrak-Nolte et al. 1990; Cook 1992; Chen et al. 1993; Peterson et al. 1993; Hildyard et al. 2005; Jaeger et al. 2007; Vilhelm et al. 2011), also referred by several different names such as the slip interface model (Schoenberg 1980) or imperfect interface model (Rokhlin and Wang 1991), is used here. This model represents a fracture as a non-welded contact between two homogeneous, isotropic, and linear elastic half spaces. The non-welded contact is assumed to have the following boundary conditions: (a) the stress across the non-welded contact is continuous; and (b) the displacements across the non-welded contact are discontinuous. A physical analog of the displacement discontinuity model is two elastic half-spaces coupled by a set of distributed springs, in which the spring constant per area is analogous to the fracture stiffness (Pyrak-Nolte 1996). The discontinuity in displacement is inversely proportional to the specific stiffness of the fracture. For a fracture located on the x-y plane, the boundary condition representing the fracture is (Schoenberg 1980):

$$[u_j] = \kappa_{ij}^{-1} \sigma_{zi} \quad (i, j = x, y, z) \quad (2)$$

where $[u_j]$ is the displacement discontinuity across the fracture, κ_{ij} is the fracture stiffness matrix, and σ_{zi} are components of the stress tensor on the fracture (σ_{zx} and σ_{zy} are tangential stresses, σ_{zz} is the normal stress). By definition, the ratio between the stress and the magnitude of the associated displacement discontinuity is the specific stiffness of the fracture (Goodman et al. 1968).

The transmission and reflection coefficients for a rock discontinuity depend on the fracture stiffness, frequency of the signal, and the seismic impedances of intact material (product of density and seismic velocity) for shear waves. Figure 9 shows the theoretical prediction of the wave

transmission and reflection coefficients as a function of the normalized frequency (the frequency is normalized by the ratio of the fracture specific stiffness to the seismic impedance, i.e. normalized frequency = $\omega Z / \kappa$) (Pyrak-Nolte et al. 1990).

When the stiffness of a fracture approaches zero ($\kappa \rightarrow 0$), the transmission coefficient decreases to zero and the reflection coefficient increases to one. In this case, the fracture behaves as a free surface. In contrast, when the fracture stiffness approaches infinity ($\kappa \rightarrow \infty$), the fracture behaves as a welded contact for which all the energy is transmitted across the fracture without any reflection. The displacement discontinuity theory shows that a fracture behaves as a low-pass filter that attenuates the wave by reducing the high-frequency components of the signal. A fracture only passes frequencies that are lower than its characteristic frequency, $\omega_c = 2\kappa/Z$ (Yale et al. 1995). According to the displacement discontinuity theory, the specific stiffness of a fracture can be determined experimentally based on the transmission and reflection coefficients of the wave propagated through the fracture. For waves propagating normal to the fracture, the fracture specific stiffness as a function of frequency can be written as (Choi et al. 2014):

$$\kappa_z(\omega) = \frac{\omega \rho V_p}{2} \left| \frac{T}{R} \right| \quad (3)$$

$$\kappa_x(\omega) = \frac{\omega \rho V_s}{2} \left| \frac{T}{R} \right| \quad (4)$$

where κ_z and κ_x are the discontinuity normal and shear specific stiffnesses, V_p and V_s are the compressional and shear wave velocities of the intact material, respectively, and ρ is the density of the material. This approach assumes that the length of travel paths in the bulk material is the same for transmission and reflection.

Fracture specific stiffness was calculated for the fractured Indiana limestone specimens, based on seismic transmission and reflection measurements, using equation (4). The dominant frequency for the shear wave signals was 0.34 MHz at 4 MPa of normal stress. Considering the average wave velocity for shear waves, $V_s=2500$ m/s, the wavelength of the signal is equal to 7.14 mm. Figure 10 shows the shear stress-displacement and the calculated fracture specific stiffness for an Indiana limestone specimen at a 4 MPa normal stress.

A peak in the fracture shear specific stiffness (Figure 10) occurred prior to the peak shear strength of the discontinuity. The peak in the fracture specific stiffness is then followed by a significant drop as shear failure occurred. The peak is indicative of the impending failure of the specimen and is the cause of the precursors observed on the transmitted and reflected signal amplitudes. Figure 11 shows the shear fracture specific stiffness at the moment of failure as a function of frequency, confirming that the fracture specific stiffness is indeed frequency dependent. A frequency-dependent stiffness indicates the heterogeneity (or lack of homogeneity) of the probability distribution of fracture specific stiffness (Pyrak-Nolte and Nolte 1992; Acosta-Colon et al. 2009).

6.2. Static fracture stiffness measurement

In this study, DIC technique was used to obtain the in-plane displacement field at the surface of the Indiana limestone specimen by comparing digital images taken during the experiment.

DIC provided the vertical displacement contour on the specimen surface as a function of time during the experiment. From the vertical displacement contour, the relative vertical (shear) displacement between the two sides of the discontinuity (fracture) along the entire height of the discontinuity was obtained. Figure 12 shows the vertical displacement contour at the moment of shear failure. To quantify the amount of shear displacement along the height of the discontinuity,

profiles of vertical displacement are extracted from the displacement contours. As mentioned earlier, the displacement measurement with DIC involves matching subsets of images through a matching process. Because the discontinuity between the limestone blocks is the location of large displacement gradients, two vertical cross sections that are each 2 mm apart from the discontinuity (4 mm apart from each other) are selected to determine the relative shear displacements (fracture shear displacements) between the two blocks (the cross sections are shown in dashed lines in Figure 12). Because these two cross sections are closest ones to the discontinuity, the relative values of the shear displacement between these two cross sections in fact are equal to the fracture's shear displacement. In other words, the elastic shear deformation of the intact material (matrix) is excluded from the measurements. The vertical displacement profiles along 4 horizontal cross sections at the moment of failure are shown in Figure 13. The discontinuity in displacement for the fracture as shown in grey is clearly visible between $x=23$ mm and $x=27$ mm. This differentiates the fracture's shear displacement from the intact (matrix) displacement. Figure 14 shows the the fracture's shear displacement at different stages of the test along the height of the fracture. The average value of fracture's shear displacement along the height of the fracture (discontinuity) at any moment is considered as the fracture's shear displacement at that specific moment. Figure 15a shows the applied shear stress and relative shear displacement along the entire discontinuity as a function of the applied shear displacement measured by the LVDT. The applied shear stress shows an increase with shear displacement with a moderate increase in slope, while the average relative shear displacement shows more rapid changes in the slope.

The ratio between an increment of the applied shear stress to the corresponding increment of the relative shear displacement (slip) defines the static shear stiffness. Figure 15a contains the graphs of applied shear stress and measured relative shear displacement along the entire discontinuity as

a function of shear displacement. Figure 15b shows the relative shear displacement as a function of the applied shear stress. The slope of this curve indicates the ratio of the increment in the relative shear displacement to the increment in the applied shear stress, and is by definition shear compliance or the inverse of static shear stiffness. The static shear stiffness is calculated by determining the inverse of the slope of this curve (Figure 15b) and is shown in Figure 15c. The resulting shear stiffness is for the entire area of the discontinuity.

At the early stages of the test, the shear stress shows an increase while the rate of increase in the relative shear displacement (slip) along the entire discontinuity is small. This results in high values of static shear stiffness at the early stages of the test. With further acceleration in slip along the discontinuity, the fracture shear stiffness is reduced to more representative values and a clear loss of static shear stiffness is observed prior to the failure of the specimen. It should be noted that the static shear stiffness calculated by DIC is based on the measurements made on the surface of the specimen while dynamic stiffness measurements obtained from the seismic wave propagation are representative of the interior of the specimen and discontinuity.

7. Comparison Between Static and Dynamic Fracture Stiffness

The static shear stiffness is defined as the shear stress increment required for a unit increment of shear displacement. Dynamic and static fracture stiffness are closer at low frequencies (< 0.1 MHz) (Pyrak-Nolte and Nolte 1992). For laboratory ultrasonic frequencies, the dynamic fracture stiffness is usually greater than the static fracture stiffness. Pyrak-Nolte et al. (1990) performed laboratory experiments on single natural fractures in quartz-monzonite and found that dynamic normal specific stiffness values were roughly four to eight times larger than the statically determined values. It is suggested that such discrepancy is, in part, due to the frequency-dependent nature of

dynamic fracture stiffness (Pyrak-Nolte and Nolte 1992). A comparison between the static fracture shear stiffness (Figure 15c) and the dynamic fracture stiffness (Figure 10) reveals that the dynamic fracture stiffness, measured by seismic wave propagation, is roughly five to ten times greater than the static fracture stiffness, measured by DIC. Also, Barton (2007) reported that dynamic shear stiffnesses may be up to two orders of magnitude stiffer than static shear stiffnesses. Therefore, our observation is consistent with previous observations in the literature supporting the fact that the static and dynamic fracture stiffnesses are different both in terms of normal and shear stiffnesses. It should be noted that the fracture static and dynamic stiffness values measured at lower seismic exploration frequencies would be closer than the values measured at laboratory ultrasonic frequencies. In the calculation of the static stiffness, the overall shear stress applied to the discontinuity and the resulting shear displacements are used. Thus, the static shear stiffness is a representative value for the entire area of the discontinuity while the dynamic shear stiffness measured by seismic wave propagation method is representative of the shear stiffness for the contacting surfaces within the focus area of the seismic transducers.

8. Conclusions

A number of direct shear experiments were performed to investigate the static and dynamic fracture shear stiffness using seismic wave propagation and digital image correlation. An instrumented direct shear apparatus was used to subject fractured specimens of Indiana limestone to shear failure while simultaneously measuring the seismic waves transmitted through and reflected from the fracture as well as digital images from the contacting surfaces. Two innovative techniques of seismic wave propagation and digital image correlation were used to measure the shear stiffness of rock fractures. Fracture specific stiffness is calculated as the ratio of an increment in stress to the resulting increment in displacement. This definition is valid for both static and

dynamic loading conditions and for normal and shear stiffness. To experimentally determine shear stiffness of a fracture, the relative shear displacement between the two sides of the fracture, as a function of static stress, was measured. To determine dynamic normal and shear stiffnesses, the transmission and reflection coefficients of waves normally incident on the fracture were used with the displacement discontinuity model. The dynamic shear stiffness measured by seismic wave propagation showed five to ten times greater values than the static shear stiffness values. This discrepancy between the static and dynamic measurements is explained by the differences in frequency and strain amplitudes used in measurements.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank Dr. Antonio Bobet and Dr. Laura Pyrak-Nolte of Purdue University for providing valuable feedback on the experimental program and the technical content of the paper.

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Tables

Table 1 – Unconfined compression strength of Indiana limestone (Ruffolo and Shakoor 2009)

Mean	Minimum	Maximum	Standard deviation
53.8 MPa	28 MPa	64.4 MPa	6.46 MPa

List of Figure Captions

FIG. 1- DIC Fundamentals

FIG. 2- (a) Setup for fracturing the Indiana limestone blocks, (b) fractured Indiana limestone specimens; (c) the contact surfaces after fracturing.

FIG. 3- (a) Surface roughness measurements on the contact surface, (b) histogram of asperity heights.

FIG. 4- Direct shear apparatus with embedded transducers. Inset: Transducer layout for seismic measurements

FIG. 5- (a) Shear stress-displacement plot for Indiana limestone specimens; (b) failure envelope obtained for peak and residual strengths

FIG. 6- Waveforms transmitted through and reflected off the fractured Indiana limestone specimen as a function of the applied normal stress

FIG. 7- Waveforms transmitted through and reflected off the fractured Indiana limestone during a shear experiment with 3 MPa confinement

FIG. 8- Shear stress-displacement and shear wave amplitudes for specimen under 4 MPa of normal stress

FIG. 9- Magnitudes of the reflection and transmission coefficients for a seismic wave normal to a discontinuity, as a function of normalized frequency (after Choi et al. 2014).

FIG. 10- Shear stress-displacement and fracture shear specific stiffness for specimen under 4 MPa normal stress

FIG. 11- Fracture shear specific stiffness as a function of frequency

FIG. 12- Vertical displacement contour at shear failure moment (peak shear stress)

FIG. 13- Vertical displacement profiles at four cross sections ($y=25$ mm; $y=50$ mm; $y=100$ mm; and $y=125$ mm)

FIG. 14- Relative vertical displacement profiles along the discontinuity at different stages of the test as a function of shear displacement and shear stress

FIG. 15- (a) Shear stress and relative shear displacement, (b) relative shear displacement versus shear stress, (c) static shear stiffness versus shear stress

Reference image

Deformed image

(a) Image matching process: a reference square subset before deformation and a target (or deformed) subset after deformation

(b) Distribution of the cross-correlation (CC) coefficient

FIG 1- DIC fundamentals

(a)

(b)

(c)

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(a)

(b)

FIG. 3- (a) Surface roughness measurements on the contact surface, (b) histogram of asperity heights. Note: The blue strip in the surface roughness plot shows the location of the drill bit and the data from this strip is not included in the histogram of asperity height.

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(a)

(b)

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(b) Reflected shear wave (3S)

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